

**AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF HERPES IN
PERIODONTAL PRACTICE**

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ABSTRACT. Most people can claim that they have not experienced any manifestations of a herpes infection, but this does not prove that it is not in the blood. According to WHO statistics, by the age of 18, the herpes simplex virus is found in 99% of people. According to the mechanism of infection, herpes infection can be divided into congenital and acquired. Acquired infection is primary and secondary (recurrent). The present study involved 30 people diagnosed with chronic recurrent herpes. All patients were divided into 2 groups: the 1st control group (15 people), traditional drug treatment was carried out using antiviral drugs. The 2nd group - the working group (15 people) received, in addition to the generally accepted scheme, the last-generation antiviral drug Vivorax. A positive result in a shorter time was obtained in the 2nd group of patients receiving the latest generation antiviral drug, it should be noted that not only epithelialization of the elements of the lesion, but also an improvement in the general condition in patients of this group was ascertained on the 3rd visit, in patients Group 1 — after 7 visits. The data of the analysis of the immediate and long-term results of herpes treatment with the inclusion of the last generation antiviral effect in the treatment regimen allow it to be recommended for clinical use in the practice of periodontists.

Keywords: herpes, infectious disease, antiviral drug

Infectious pathology, including those caused by the herpes virus, is today an urgent problem not only in general medicine, but also at a practical appointment with a periodontist.

Herpetic eruptions often appear on the face and in the oral cavity, and patients create a real danger of infecting others. It is known that the infection of the adult population with the herpes simplex virus reaches almost 100%, and in children under the age of 15 it approaches 80%. Among lip diseases, the infection caused by the herpes virus ranks third after candidiasis and leukoplakia. Herpes viruses can enter the human body through damaged skin and mucous membranes. The severity of clinical manifestations is determined by the severity and nature of the manifestation and symptoms of general intoxication.

Herpes simplex in adults is diagnosed more often as a recurrent form of the disease that occurs in people who have had previously clinically pronounced herpes against the background of circulating antibodies in the body. Recurrent herpes labialis is the clinical result of the activation of a latent viral infection in the nerve ganglia. They also note the fixed nature of vesicular eruptions at the sites of the appearance of earlier elements of the lesion.

Carious lesions were diagnosed in 80% of patients with fixed herpes. Sharp edges of teeth, periodontal pathology. The hygienic condition of the oral cavity is not satisfactory, which also complicated the course of chronic herpetic infection in the oral cavity. 45% of patients needed re-prosthetics and replacement of fillings; 33% of patients required prosthetics due to partial secondary adentia.

The aim of the study is to optimize an integrated approach to the treatment of herpes using the latest generation of antiviral drugs.

Materials and methods

The present study involved 30 people diagnosed with chronic recurrent herpes. The age of patients is from 20 to 50 years. The duration of the disease ranged from 5 months to 6 years. All patients were divided into 2 groups:

The 1st control group (15 people) received traditional medical treatment using antiviral drugs.

The 2nd group - the working group (15 people) received, in addition to the generally accepted scheme, the latest generation antiviral drug "Vivorax".

Pic. 1. Fixed herpes in the corner of the mouth on the left.

Pic. 2. Application at the time of defeat.

All patients underwent a general clinical study for the carriage of the herpes virus type 1. On the first visit, a thorough survey was conducted, which includes identifying complaints, please describe in detail the nature of the sensations during the appearance of erosions on the red border of the lips, the frequency of exacerbations, when the elements of the lesion were first diagnosed, what preceded this. Attention was paid to the previous treatment, its effectiveness.

Identification of the number of relapses, frequency and duration.

In the complex therapy for patients of the 2nd group after oxygen therapy, the latest generation antiviral drug was used in an ointment composition on the elements of the lesion. The mechanism of the therapeutic effect of this dosage form is the inhibition, replication of viral attacks, which reduces the viral load.

The most sensitive to the drug: herpes simplex virus, adenoviruses, paramyxoviruses, hantoviruses, reoviruses.

Research results

In the course of treatment, a positive result was obtained in a shorter period of time in the 2nd group of patients receiving the latest generation antiviral drug. It should be noted that not only epithelialization of the elements of the lesion, but also an

improvement in the general condition in patients of this group was noted on the 3rd visit (pic 3), in patients of the 1st group, clinical well-being came only after 7 visits.

Pic. 3 Fixed herpes in the stage of epithelialization.

In the process of observation, it was noted that in patients receiving such a treatment regimen, the remission period for the appearance of elements in the area of the mucous membrane of the lips was extended.

Pic. 4. Healing of a herpetic rash.

The data of the analysis of the immediate and long-term results of herpes treatment with the inclusion of the last generation antiviral effect in the treatment regimen allow us to recommend it for clinical use in the practical use of periodontists.

Conclusion

Our clinical study of the approach to the treatment of herpes of the oral mucosa with the inclusion of the latest generation antiviral drug in the regimen made it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of this technique in clinical cases and recommend practical dentistry for use.

We believe that the effectiveness of the proposed approaches to the treatment of herpes will help reduce the percentage of complications and further prevent malignization of the elements of the lesion.

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